

Rain of Peace- A ritual of Rain

2 Comments / Blog / By Deepanshu Giri

Indra- The god of Thunder and Rains and he is the one responsible for all the wealth, comfort and peace in life he blesses humans in the form of Rain, Indra being the king was never liked by devils and other creatures who use to live realms down below as when it rains, water has to get accumulated inside the earth as the earth is getting healed with all the creatures living inside earth coming out in rainy season.

Sun is about to enter into cancer on the 17th of July and this is marked as sowing season not only for Earth but also for humans, As the Earth is ready to accept new plants and seeds in a perfect humid environment. In the month of July first week when the monsoon starts earth not only gets moist and the temperature and humidity are perfect for growth but also all the insects living down under the earth also come out and the earth goes through a reset.

The effect of weather also happens on the mental condition of humans as this is the perfect time to work on emotional health and take out all those things which are hidden inside you and sow some new thoughts and ideas and this time happy ones- Water has a property to cleanse and not only the

physical body but the emotional body to, That is why taking a walk in light rain is something soul-soothing which helps you get connected to Sky.

Sun in Cancer is going to bring a lot of emotional challenges and issues which you never want to discuss even with yourself as they are exactly like worms coming out and leaving place for new ideas, When you have malefic in the sign of cancer or any major planets placed in Cancer- One of the ways will be to take shower in rain as much as you can, Do not miss the nectar coming from the sky, this is as close as you can get to things in the sky, its blessings from Indra.

Indra is the god of wealth as he controls rain, He is the one capable to deliver goods from the Sky to earth, He controls how comfortable you can live on earth and that is why rains have such a special place in the life of humans, Indra not only heals you via rain but also punishes you via rain, Sometimes in life, it feels like problems are being delivered from Sky and one of them is done by Ketu -which I have discussed in another blog, Another sign which is a moksha than and is connected to Sky is Cancer, Planets in Cancer Zodiac or Moon in their dasa will create mental troubles related to the house significations.

Cancer is a watery sign and this sign shows your emotional body, this sign is so critical that it decides the way you feel about anything in life and when you have malefic in this sign, This creates emotional scars for life, A lot of students asks what is difference between Cancer Sign and 4th house and which is a very valid point for example if the ascendant is rising with Virgo then 4th house which is your mother/emotional body will be Saggitarius and where does this leave with Cancer sign?

One of the Remedies in this month is to offer all the insects and worms coming out of the earth food as Indra rules Jyestha(the last part of Scorpio) which is a symbolic expression that till the end of all realms, it is the world of Indra but his kingdom starts from Kritika as Agni being the best friend of Indra and always protecting the interest of a King – Agni is basically the idea generating capacity and being the number one in any field, for King to rule for many years, to be always new, pure and pious is the key.

Why not Ashvini is the starting point for the kingdom of Indra? – Ashwins do not go along with Indra as Indra refused to give Ashvins the status of God due to body deformity and considered them as mortals while the next nakshatra belongs to Yam-Bharani which is again about people bearing the load in the mortal world and paying for sins, that is why in some textbooks you will find nakshatra mala starting from Kritika rather than from Ashvini.

To help all the insects, worms and other creatures coming out of the earth to be fed with milk and Jaggery products and again I am sure most students of astrology can figure it out (Please tell others in the comment section.)

Planting of Trees is to be done this month and try to plant as much as you can as by doing this you are replaying earth, this is like paying your yearly EMI, so that you can live on this earth peacefully, To be thankful to your mother who provided you nutrition, a place to live and give you chance to pay

back, Jupiter is the planet exalted here as you can see how bad is weather, so consuming – chickpea flour on daily basis, sweets related to Chickpea, milk and Jaggery and offering same to others will be helpful.

One another thing that happens during this time period is your Vaat gets imbalanced which is an airy element that is why you will see a lot of people being emotional or cannot handle stress in this month for them the remedy is in a ritual done in north India to give out Ghewar which is a traditional Indian Sweet- which is deep fried in desi ghee (Jupiter+Saturn) and then covered with Khoya (A milk product).

One of the traditional remedies and ritual do be done from Monday onwards is to offer sweet Besan Pakore to Pipal, Banyan, Amla, Shami, Banana or Akra Tree daily in the evening and offering milk and Money to Ground and recite this chant after offerings and although this is said to be for huge wealth moreover this will provide you peace on this earth which is far more valuable than any asset.

<https://youtube.com/watch?v=4VnLaJQODvY%3Ffeature%3Doembed>

Think about it – think deeper about when to use which sign – I have taught this over and over again in different courses such as Yogini and Predictive -2, In this blog, I am only focusing on the Cancer sign not the sign present on the 4th house. The use of Chandra Kundali is to see how the native is taking any dasa based on the feeling only, the native is going to explain the problems, It is one of the far greatest and simplest tools of Jyotish, which need to be used in every chart, Use of Chandra Kanal chakra is another tool which is to be used, Strength of any chart depends on Quality of Moon and Dispositor of Moon and if these two are well placed, native does well in life.

In the Chart of Sh Narendra Modi Ji-Libra Rising and Moon Mars in 2nd house- Moon Mahadasa running and you can see in the last 10 years there were several moments where he cried, got emotional but since Moon is house wise exalted and rasi wise debilitated – created a sense of deception for the native as what others see as his loss, there is something else going on at the back.

Once the Mars Dasa will take over, He will not be that soft or emotional but go on a track of Mars Scorpio, while let us take the example of a common person.

In this Chart look at Moon and Dispositor and you will find pretty good clues- Moon is in the 9th house which is not a good house for Moon as a lot of responsibility of father and siblings will come to the native but the disposition of a Moon is house wise exalted and shows a lot of things will be achieved by native due to father's blessings and this native took over his family business from one small shop and turned in to a brand in the city.

10th from Moon is Venus placed in own house aspected by Mars and Jupiter – native is in the business of Food industry, and currently running Jupiter MD- The issue or question he asked was about Money- (2nd from Moon) as a lot of money is going in property and construction (Mars sitting with Jupiter and being the 4th lord from Moon). Since this is the 10th house so all the properties are professional properties, not residential ones or investment properties.

Look for your Dasa patterns from Moon Chart to see how you are feeling about the dasa, I hope I have given you some wisdom today and helped heal your soul.

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2 thoughts on “Rain of Peace- A ritual of Rain”

DINESH JEENGAR

31 JULY 2023 AT 12:16

Such a fascinating and enlightening read! Exploring the significance of Indra, the god of Thunder and Rains, and his role in bringing wealth, comfort, and peace to our lives is truly captivating. The connection between Sun entering Cancer and the sowing season, both for Earth and humans, is remarkable. I'm intrigued by how weather affects our mental condition and how we can work on our emotional health during this time. The remedies and rituals shared to honor Indra and maintain balance in life are truly insightful. Thanks for this soul-soothing piece!

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ANIKET SHRIVASTAVA

6 AUGUST 2023 AT 17:10

Hello Deepanshu Sir,

Please provide a time slot for atleast 45 mins for a consultation with you. Honestly, till date I have not seen someone with so much detailed explanations on various aspects of birth chart. Would be very thankful to you if you can provide an appointment.

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